

Synthesis and in vitro evaluation of new oxadiazole thioethers as antibacterials

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Abstract

A study was conducted to synthesize a new set of compounds named **comp.4–7** using the 1,3,4 tautomer of oxadiazole as the centroid unit. These compounds were subjected to various characterization processes, including thin-layer chromatography, infrared spectroscopy, and ¹HNMR spectroscopy. The study was based on previous research that established several compounds' diverse range of biological activities, such as hydrazide Schiff's bases (hydrazones), oxadiazoles, thiophenes, and isoxazoles. These compounds had been found to possess properties against bacteria, fungi, TB, viruses, cancer cells, and inflammatory responses, as well as analgesic properties. The results of the docking study were conducted in MOE software, targeting the largest binding site of *E. coli* gyrase B (PDB: 6YD9) as identified by SITE FINDER, suggesting that these compounds had great potential to be effective antibacterial agents. To evaluate the synthesized compounds antibacterial activities, the well diffusion method was used, and the findings revealed that the synthesized compounds exhibit slight to moderate activities against *E. coli*, *S. aureus*, and *K. pneumoniae*.

Keywords

oxadiazoles, Schiff's base, thiophenes, isoxazoles, antibacterial

Introduction

Heterocyclic compounds play a vital role in pharmaceutical and material sciences, and oxadiazole is one of the most widely used compounds due to its diverse properties. Among the structural isomers of oxadiazole, 1,3,4-oxadiazole is of particular interest in medicinal chemistry as a promising pharmacophore for developing new drugs with a wide range of activities (Balaji et al. 2015; Al-Mulla 2017; Kim et al. 2023).

Isoxazole is another five-membered heterocycle having two heteroatoms, which are oxygen and nitrogen, at the adjacent positions. Isoxazole compounds possess many biological activities that are explained by a wide spectrum of protein targets that isoxazole compounds are possible

to interact with, such as anticancer, antibacterial, antifungal, antiviral, and anti-inflammatory (Zhu et al. 2018).

Thiophenes and their derivatives are an important class of heterocyclic compounds that possess a wide spectrum of biological properties, such as antibacterial and antifungal, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and antitumor (Shah and Verma 2018; Metwally et al. 2023).

In medicinal chemistry, new compounds with improved biological activity can be created by hybridization, which involves combining two or more distinct molecules. Hydrazones [Hydrazide Schiff's base derivatives] can be considered scaffolds because they possess great potential for various pharmaceutical applications because of their high reactivity and excellent affinity toward numerous biological targets, so they are an at-

Synthesis of the first intermediate; comp. 1:

A precise amount of vanillic acid weighing (7.0 g, 42 mmol) was mixed with methanol, and the resulting solution was cooled to 0 °C. Concentrated H₂SO₄ (5 mL) was then slowly added drop by drop to the solution, which was stirred at room temperature [before being refluxed for 7 hrs] for 48 hours. TLC results indicate the formation of a product. A precipitate formed with time when the solution was transferred into a crushed ice contained in a suitable beaker, and after the complete precipitation, NaHCO₃ (10%) was added wisely until pH was slightly alkaline to get rid of any excess acid and to neutralize the H₂SO₄. The product was collected by filtration and dried. The desired product was obtained as a yield of 7.0 g through this process (Abbas et al. 2021).

Comp. 1: whitish-brown powder, yield 91%, M.P: 60–62 °C.

ATR-FTIR spectrum in cm⁻¹: (1686) C=O stretching vibration, (1276) C-(C=O)-O stretching vibration of aromatic ester.

¹HNMR (500 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) in ppm.: 9.99(1H, *br s*, Ar-OH), 7.46–7.42(2H, *m*, aromatic protons at positions 2 and 6), 6.88–6.84(1H, *d*, aromatic proton at position 5), 3.80(3H, *s*, COOCH₃), and 3.83(3H, *s*, OCH₃).

Synthesis of the second intermediate; comp. 2:

Comp.1 was dissolved in hot absolute ethanol (99.9%) using 5 mL. The amount of **Comp.1** (27 mmol), which is equivalent to (5.0 g). Then, 80% hydrazine hydrate (270 mmol, 13.5 g) was added to the solution gradually. The reaction was monitored by TLC to track the progress of the reaction, and the results of TLC indicate that 4 hrs as reflux time was required. The reaction system was left to cool to r.t with overnight stirring and cooling, and a white precipitate formed as a solid mass, which was washed with cold ethanol, filtered out, and dried. The product yield was found to be 3.5 g after completion of the drying process (Yaseen et al. 2022).

Comp. 2: white powder, yield 70%, M.P: 208–210 °C.

ATR-FTIR spectrum in cm⁻¹: (3310) phenolic OH stretching vibration overlapped with NH₂ asymmetric stretching vibration, (3256) NH amide stretching vibration, (3210) NH₂ symmetric stretching vibration, (1628) C=O stretching vibration of amide, (1600) NH bending vibration, and (1585) NH bending vibration of amide.

¹HNMR (400MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) in ppm: 9.52(2H, *s*, CONH and Ar-OH), 7.4–7.29(2H, *m*, aromatic protons at positions 2 and 6), 6.84–6.76(1H, *d*, aromatic proton at position 5), 4.38(2H, *s*, NH-NH₂), and 3.78(3H, *s*, OCH₃).

Synthesis of the third intermediate; comp. 3:

A compound mixture was prepared by suspending **comp.2** (6.86 mmol, 1.25 g) in 30 mL of 50% ethanol. CS₂ (0.0103 mmol, 0.785 g) was then added to the mixture and stirred for a few minutes. Next, KOH (10.3 mmol, 0.7 g) was introduced, and the whole mixture was refluxed

for 12 hours. The progress of the reaction was monitored by TLC, and the evolution of H₂S was noted for better observation. Upon completion of the refluxing process, conc. HCl was added dropwise to a beaker containing the reaction solution and 30 mL of crushed ice. Precipitate began to be formed and increased until the pH of the mixture became 2–3 [no further precipitate was formed]. The precipitate was then filtered, dried, and purified using the base to dissolve the product and then acidification to reform the pure product, which was 0.9 g (Karabanovich et al. 2016).

Comp. 3: faint yellow powder, yield 59%, M.P: 186–189 °C.

ATR-FTIR spectrum in cm⁻¹: (3452) phenolic OH stretching vibration, (3155) NH (*br stretching*), 2670(*w*) SH stretching vibration.

¹HNMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) in ppm.: 14.58(1H, *s*, -SH), 10.04(1H, *s*, Ar-OH), 7.37–7.3(2H, *m*, aromatic protons at positions 2 and 6), 6.94–6.92(1H, *d*, aromatic proton at position 5), and 3.84(3H, *s*, OCH₃).

Synthesis of the first final product; comp.4:

A chemical compound known as **comp.3**, weighing (2.23 mmol, 0.5 g) was dissolved completely in 5 mL of absolute ethanol. To the solution, triethylamine (0.00223 mmol or 0.22564 g) was added gradually, and after a few minutes of gentle and constant stirring, [4-(chloromethyl) benzaldehyde (0.00223 mmol or 0.345 g)] was added to the mixture. The solution was heated gently to a temperature of about 50 °C, which resulted in the formation of a precipitate. The precipitate was then filtered, dried, and finally crystallized from a mixture of boiled absolute ethanol and 2-methoxy ethanol (Hassan et al. 2023). This process led to the formation of a pure final product, which weighed 0.5 g.

Comp. 4: white crystals, yield 65.5%, M.P: 167–169 °C.

ATR-FTIR spectrum in cm⁻¹: (3417–2830) broad phenolic OH stretching vibration, (2735) CH stretching vibration of aldehyde, and (1697) C=O stretching vibration of aldehyde carbonyl.

¹HNMR (400MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) in ppm: 9.98(1H, *s*, Ar-OH), 9.97(1H, *s*, COH), 7.9–7.88(2H, *d*, aromatic protons at positions 10 and 12), 7.71–7.69(2H, *d*, aromatic protons at positions 9 and 13), 7.41–7.38(2H, *m*, aromatic protons at positions 2 and 6), 6.95–6.93(1H, *d*, aromatic proton at position 5), 4.65(2H, *s*, -S-CH₂), and 3.85(3H, *s*, OCH₃).

Synthesis of the second final product; comp.5:

Comp.4 (0.3 mmol, 0.1 g) was suspended in 5 mL of absolute ethanol. Three drops of glacial acetic acid were added to the suspension with constant stirring for 15 minutes. Then, 4-hydroxybenzohydrazide (0.3 mmol, 0.044 g) was added to the mixture, and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 30 minutes. During this process, the suspension became a clear solution. The reaction mixture was then allowed to stir gently overnight. The formed precipitate was filtered and dried. The excess solvent was evaporated, and the product was crystallized from hot absolute ethanol. The final yield of pure product was 0.09 g (Han et al. 2018).

Comp. 5: white powder, yield 65%, M.P: 230–232 °C.

ATR-FTIR spectrum in cm^{-1} : (3418) stretching vibration of two phenolic OH, (3244) NH amide stretching vibration, (1647) C=O stretching vibration of amide carbonyl, and (1608) C=N stretching vibration of imine.

^1H NMR (400MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$) in ppm: 11.64(1H, s, CONH), 10.12(1H, s, Ar-OH⁺), 9.96(1H, s, Ar-OH), 8.41(1H, s, -N=CH-), [7.81–7.79, 7.7–7.68, 7.56–7.54] (6H, d, aromatic protons at positions 9, 10, 12, 13, 17, and 21), 7.43–7.39(2H, m, aromatic protons at positions 2, and 6), 6.96–6.94(1H, d, aromatic proton at position 5), 6.87–6.85(2H, d, aromatic protons at positions 18, and 20), 4.6(2H, s, -SCH₂-), and 3.86(3H, s, OCH₃).

Synthesis of the third final product; comp.6:

Comp.3, which had a weight of (0.67 mmole, 0.15 g), was dissolved in 3 mL of absolute ethanol. After that, (0.67 mmole, 0.0677 g) of triethylamine was added to the mixture and stirred for 10–15 minutes. Subsequently, (0.67 mmole, 0.1118 g) of 2-chloro-5-(chloromethyl)thiophene was added, and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 2 hours. Once the refluxing was complete, D.W. was added until a precipitate appeared, and the mixture was then filtered, dried, and subjected to crystallization using a two-solvent system of hot absolute ethanol and hot D.W (1:1) (Hassan et al. 2023).

Comp. 6: white crystals, yield 48%, M.P: 139–141 °C.

ATR-FTIR spectrum in cm^{-1} : (2978 and 2893) asymmetric and symmetric stretching vibration of CH₂, (1447) bending vibration of CH₂.

^1H NMR(400MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$) in ppm: 9.96(1H, s, Ar-OH), 7.44–7.42(2H, m, aromatic protons at positions 2 and 6), 7.01–6.93(3H, m, protons of thiophene ring and aromatic protons at positions 5, 9, and 10), 4.75 (2H, s, -SCH₂-), 3.86(3H, s, OCH₃).

Synthesis of the fourth final product; comp. 7:

Comp. 7 was prepared by the same procedure that was followed in the preparation of **comp. 6**, except crystallization was from hot absolute ethanol only (Hassan et al. 2023).

Comp. 7: white crystals, yield 47%, M.P: 116–118 °C.

ATR-FTIR spectrum in cm^{-1} : (2982 and 2835) asymmetric and symmetric stretching vibration of CH₂, (1632) stretching vibration of (-O-C=N-), (1466) asymmetric bending vibration of CH₃ and scissoring bending vibration of CH₂, (1369) symmetrical bending vibration of CH₃ groups.

^1H NMR (400MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$) signals in ppm: 9.96 (1H, s, Ar-OH), 7.43–7.4 (2H, m, aromatic protons at positions 2 and 6), 6.97–6.93 (1H, d, aromatic proton at position 5), 4.39 (2H, s, -SCH₂-), 3.85 (3H, s, OCH₃), 2.35 (3H, s, methyl protons at position near to O), 2.24 (3H, s, methyl protons at position near to N).

Molecular induced fit (flexible) docking study

Molecular docking investigations were conducted on the *E. coli* DNA-binding protein 6YD9 (DNA Gyrase), leveraging its high-resolution (1.60 Å) crystal structure derived from X-ray crystallography. The protein is composed of

a single chain (chain A) harboring a co-crystal ligand (ON2) binding site. Docking was executed on chain A following preparatory measures encompassing water removal, binding site delineation, and hydrogen addition. The AMBER10 force field was employed for energy minimization purposes. The MOE 2022 software facilitated molecular docking, with the SMILE representations of the investigated compounds generated via ChemBioDraw Ultra 13.0. These were subsequently transformed into 3D configurations within MOE 2022, followed by protonation and energy minimization utilizing the AMBER 10 force field with a 0.1 Å RMSD. Validation of the docking procedure involved re-docking the co-crystallized ligand (NO2). An RMSD value of 1.18 Å, computed using Discovery Studio Visualizer and VMD, substantiated the precision of the MOE program for docking the novel ligands (Prieto-Martinez et al. 2019; Hamdoon and Hadi 2024).

Antibacterial assay

To examine inhibition bacterial growth related to the synthesized compounds, diffusion assays were performed. In which McFarland turbidity of 0.5, having a concentration of around 1.5×10^8 colony-forming units per milliliter, was the standard to compare with the prepared bacterial suspension. The inoculated mixture was applied to the surface Mueller-Hinton agar plates. After inoculation, a current of sterile air under a hood was applied to remove any excess liquid. To assess the efficacy of the synthesized compounds in combating bacterial growth, in each agar plate of the examined bacteria, four wells were created. Then, 80 µl of each concentration of the compounds, at 1000 µg/mL, were poured into these wells. These plates were placed in an incubator set at 37 °C for 24 hours. Following the incubation period, the diameter of the inhibition zone formed around each well was measured to determine the potency of the targeted compounds (Bauer et al. 1966).

Results and discussion

Chemistry

A successful multi-step reaction process was executed, which involved the synthesis of several new compounds, as shown in Fig. 2. The process involved various chemical changes, starting with esterification of a carboxylic acid with an alcohol in the presence of an acid catalyst (Smith 2017). This produced the initial compound, **Comp. 1**, which was analyzed using various techniques. The FTIR spectrum of **Comp. 1** showed a significant carbonyl group of aromatic ester at 1686 cm^{-1} , while the ^1H NMR analysis confirmed the presence of COOCH₃ at 3.8 ppm.

Next, **Comp. 1** was refluxed in absolute ethanol with hydrazine hydrate 80% to produce **Comp. 2** (Sabzi and Al-Mudhafar 2023). The FTIR spectrum of Comp.2 was characterized by doublet bands (asymmetric and symmetric) for the primary amine of hydrazide at 3310 cm^{-1} and 3210 cm^{-1} , respectively, and 3256 cm^{-1} NH amide

stretching. Additionally, the 1628 cm^{-1} C=O stretching of amide and 1600 cm^{-1} of NH_2 bending were observed. The presence of CONH at 9.53 ppm and 2H as a singlet for NH_2 at 4.38 ppm were confirmed by $^1\text{H NMR}$ analysis.

Furthermore, **Comp. 3** was obtained by refluxing the ethanolic suspension of **Comp. 2** with CS_2 in the presence of KOH (Saoud 2017). The FTIR spectrum of **Comp. 3** was characterized by the phenolic OH stretching vibration at 3452 cm^{-1} , the NH stretching vibration at 3155 cm^{-1} , weak SH stretching at 2670 cm^{-1} , and the absence of the amide band at 1628 cm^{-1} . The $^1\text{H NMR}$ spectrum showed the appearance of the SH proton at 14.58 ppm as a singlet and the absence of all protons related to hydrazide.

Comp. 4, **Comp. 6**, and **Comp. 7** were obtained through a reaction between **Comp. 3** as nucleophilic species and 4-(chloromethyl) benzaldehyde (**Comp. 4**), 2-chloro-5-(chloromethyl)thiophene (**Comp. 6**), or 4-(chloromethyl)-3,5-dimethyl isoxazole (**Comp. 7**) as electrophiles in the presence of a base catalyst and absolute ethanol as reaction solvent (Karty 2018). These new compounds were carefully characterized, using various analytical techniques to confirm their structures and properties. FTIR is characterized by 2735 cm^{-1} stretching of C-H aldehyde and 1697 cm^{-1} C=O stretching of aldehyde carbonyl. **Comp. 6** showed asymmetric and symmetric CH_2 stretching at 2978 cm^{-1} and 2893 cm^{-1} , and CH_2

Figure 2. Scheme showing the stepwise synthesis of targeted compounds.

bending at 1447 cm^{-1} . **Comp. 7**, in addition to ($-\text{O}-\text{C}=\text{N}-$) stretching vibration at 1632 cm^{-1} , also showed asymmetrical stretching vibration of CH of $-\text{CH}_3$ groups at 2982 cm^{-1} , symmetric stretching vibration of CH_3 at 2835 cm^{-1} , and 1466 cm^{-1} asymmetric bending vibration of CH_3 groups.

$^1\text{H NMR}$ is characterized by the presence of a new proton at 9.97 ppm of COH as a singlet, four aromatic protons from $7.9-7.69\text{ ppm}$ related to the benzene ring of 4-(chloromethyl) benzaldehyde, and the absence of a SH proton at 14.58 ppm and instead the appearance of new two protons as a singlet at 4.65 ppm for **comp. 4**, 4.75 ppm for **comp. 6**, and 4.35 ppm for **comp. 7**, which related to $-\text{SCH}_2$. The appearance of new protons in the aromatic region due to the thiophene ring in **comp. 6**, and finally the appearance of six protons at their expected sites due to two methyl groups of 3,5-dimethylisoxazole in **comp. 7**.

Lastly, **Comp. 5** is a Schiff base product of hydrazone type obtained by reacting aldehydes with primary amines in mildly acidic conditions (Klein 2021). FTIR was characterized by the absence of aldehyde CH stretching vibration at 2735 and aldehyde carbonyl at 1697 cm^{-1} , which was replaced by imine stretching at 1608 cm^{-1} , and the presence of amide carbonyl at 1647 cm^{-1} . $^1\text{H NMR}$ revealed the presence of new protons at 11.64 ppm as singlet, which was related to CONH; at 10.12 ppm due to OH' of 4-hydroxybenzohydrazidel; at 8.41 ppm as singlet, which was related to $\text{N}=\text{CH}$; and four aromatic protons at $7.81-7.79\text{ ppm}$ and at $6.87-6.85\text{ ppm}$. This multi-step reaction process has resulted in the successful synthesis of the new compounds.

Molecular docking analysis

Molecular docking simulations were conducted in MOE software, targeting the largest binding site of *E. coli* gyrase B (PDB: 6YD9) as identified by SITE FINDER. An induced-fit docking protocol, incorporating ligand and protein flexibility, was employed. Each molecule was allowed a maximum of five interactions with the protein (Figs 3–6). The optimal docking pose for each molecule, along with its docking score and binding site information, was documented (Table 1). This data was utilized to predict the preferred binding mode and affinity. The predicted affinity for the evaluated substances with 6YD9 was considered representative of the binding free energy (ΔG) (Al-Shuaeeb et al. 2024). The results of (ΔG) indicate that all the synthesized compounds (4–7) show good affinity for binding to the target site in comparison with cocrystal ligand (ON2). The value of RMSD for all synthesized compounds less than 2 \AA indicates that the docking pose closely matches the reference structure, suggesting good predictive accuracy.

Table 1. Scores for docking of tested compounds against the target site of co-crystallized ligand are represented in ΔG values measured in kcal/mol.

Ligand	RMSD value	Docking score (Kcal/mol)
Cocrystal (ON2)	1.18	-6.28
Comp. 4	1.68	-7.26
Comp. 5	2.01	-8.06
Comp. 6	1.58	-7.43
Comp. 7	1.75	-7.95

Figure 3. Ligand (comp. 4) interactions.

Figure 4. Ligand (comp. 5) interactions.

Figure 5. Ligand (comp. 6) interactions.

Antibacterial evaluation

There are different levels of activity that can be measured using a unit called ZI. When there is no activity, ZI is equal to zero. When activity is present, ZI can range from 5 to 10 mm for slightly active, 10 to 15 mm for moder-

ately active, and more than 15 mm for highly active (Sahib and Mohammed 2020; Ali and Farhan 2023). In the study, several chemical compounds (**comp. 4–7**) were specifically targeted and evaluated for their antibacterial properties using the well diffusion technique. The antibacterial activities of these compounds were compared

Figure 6. Ligand (comp. 7) interactions.

with two standard antibacterial agents, amoxicillin and nitrofurantoin, using both gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria. In addition, a control group was established using the solvent DMSO.

At a concentration of 1000 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, four of the compounds (**comp. 4, 5, 6, and 7**) showed excellent antibacterial activity against *E. coli*, which was comparable to that of amoxicillin. Another compound (**comp. 5**) demonstrated slightly better antibacterial activity than amoxicillin when tested against *S. aureus*, but its activity was lower than that of cefixime at a concentration of 1000 $\mu\text{g/mL}$.

Furthermore, **comp. 6** showed similar activity to amoxicillin when tested against *S. aureus*, and it exhibited comparable activity to both amoxicillin and cefixime when tested against *K. pneumoniae*. Interestingly, **comp. 5** demonstrated the best activity among all derivatives tested against *S. aureus*, while showing the least activity against *E. coli*. This can be attributed to the compound's hydrophobicity, as more hydrophobic compounds tend to be more effective against gram-positive bacteria (Beale and Block 2011).

It is worth noting that none of the compounds synthesized in the study showed any significant activity against *S. pyogenes*, *B. subtilis* or *P. aeruginosa* (Table 2).

Physicochemical properties

Understanding the physicochemical characteristics of drugs is crucial to making them work better. One important factor is the partition coefficient ($\log P$), which can be computed in silico ($\text{clog} P$). It gives an idea about how drugs move around inside the human body. Interestingly, all the synthesized compounds under consideration have a $\text{clog} P$ value less than 5, which goes in accordance with a common rule called the Lipinski rule of five. Another important thing to consider is the total polar surface area (TPSA). This gives information about the surface area taken up by parts of the drug that are attracted to water. Drugs with lower TPSA values are usually better because they can pass through cell membranes more easily. So, by carefully studying these factors, it is possible to improve how well drugs work and help patients get better results from their treatments (Table 3).

Table 2. The findings of the synthesized compounds' antibacterial activities.

Comp. name	Conc. $\mu\text{g/mL}$	Gram (+)ve				Gram (-)ve	
		<i>S. pyogenes</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>K. pneumoniae</i>
Zone of inhibition (mm)							
Comp. 4	10^3	-	8	-	-	11	-
Comp. 5	10^3	-	14	-	-	10	-
Comp. 6	10^3	-	13	-	-	12	11
Comp. 7	10^3	-	6	-	-	11	-
Amoxicillin	10^3	5	13	40	28	11	11.5
Cefixime	10^3	6	16	20	6	22	13
Nitrofurantoin	10^3	9.5	21	31	17	16	20
DMSO	Solvent and control	-	-	-	-	-	-

Table 3. The properties related to physical and chemical characteristics of the compounds that were synthesized.

Comp.	ClogP	Ali class	n. H-bond acceptors	n. H-bond donors	n. rotatable bonds	TPSA / °A
Comp. 4	2.92	Moderately soluble	6	1	6	110.75
Comp. 5	3.50	Poorly soluble	9	3	9	155.37
Comp. 6	3.82	Poorly soluble	5	1	5	121.92
Comp. 7	2.76	Moderately soluble	7	1	5	119.71

Table 4. Analysis of ADMET properties has been predicted for the mentioned compounds.

Comp.	CYP2C9		CYP2D6		CYP3A4		BBB	GI absorption	P-gp substrate
	S	I	S	I	S	I			
Comp. 4	P	Yes	No	No	No	Yes	No	High	No
Comp. 5	No	Yes	No	No	P	Yes	No	Low	No
Comp. 6	P	Yes	P	No	P	Yes	No	High	No
Comp. 7	No	Yes	No	No	P	Yes	No	High	Yes

S = substrate, I = inhibitor, P = probable.

Table 5. Predicted analysis of toxicity properties of the mentioned compounds.

Comp.	Hepatotoxicity*	Nephrotoxicity*	Ototoxicity*	Genotoxicity*	Neurotoxicity*	Hematotoxicity*
Comp. 4	0.646	0.271	0.292	0.819	0.34	0.126
Comp. 5	0.693	0.321	0.329	0.999	0.35	0.045
Comp. 6	0.735	0.542	0.435	0.979	0.133	0.144
Comp. 7	0.896	0.602	0.814	0.999	0.124	0.383

* Score 0 means non-toxic, while score 1 means toxic compound at targeted organ; scores between 0 and 1 indicate the compound is probably toxic.

In silico ADMET and toxicity properties

A rigorous in silico investigation of the ADMET (absorption, distribution, metabolism, excretion, and toxicity) profiles of the newly synthesized compounds was conducted employing the SwissADME cheminformatics software and ADMETlab 3.0 web server. This comprehensive analysis facilitated the identification of promising drug candidates exhibiting favorable safety profiles and the exclusion of compounds demonstrating undesirable ADMET characteristics from further progression into subsequent drug development stages. A detailed tabulation of the predicted ADMET properties for the target compounds is presented in Tables 4, 5. The scores in the table reflect the probability of toxicity of each compound (Fu et al. 2024).

Conclusion

Through a conventional synthesis method, a set of new oxadiazole-thioether derivatives was successfully developed and characterized by thin-layer chromatography, infrared spectroscopy, and ¹HNMR spectroscopy. The docking studies were conducted in MOE software, targeting the largest binding site of *E. coli* gyrase B (PDB: 6YD9). In an effort to evaluate their potential as antibacterial agents, these derivatives were tested and found to exhibit activity against *E. coli*, *K. pneumoniae*, and *S. aureus*. Notably, **Comp. 6** was found to have a particularly broad spectrum of activity. Future studies could focus on advanced mod-

eling, SAR analysis, and testing against resistant strains to enhance potency and clinical potential. Investigating combination therapies and mechanisms of action may also address antimicrobial resistance. **Comp. 6**, with its broad spectrum activity, shows promise as a lead for next-generation antibacterial agents.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The author has declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The author declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The author declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The author declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The author declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The author declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

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Author contributions

The author solely contributed to this work.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text or Supplementary Information.

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Supplementary material 1

ATR-FTIR

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Data type: pdf

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Supplementary material 2

¹H NMR

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Data type: pdf

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